

SUPERSTITIOUS BELIEFS OF ADAMAWA STATE STUDENTS IN TERTIARY INSTITUTION AS MEASURE OF LEVEL OF SCIENTIFIC LITERACY IN ADAMAWA STATE

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to determine the superstitious beliefs of Adamawa state students in tertiary institution as indicator of level of scientific literacy in Adamawa State. As public understanding of science increases, science education curriculum as bedrock for national development can move a nation economically, socially, politically and culturally forward which become a basis for sustainable development. The target population of the study comprised all students in tertiary institutions in the state. Two selected institutions were used as the sample of the study, made up of 800 students. Data collected using questionnaires were analyzed with the use of descriptive statistics in order to answer the research questions, while z-test was used to test the hypothesis. The major findings of the study showed inclination to superstition in women more than men; and the more the educational level, the less inclination to superstition. Based on the findings, it was recommended that government and other stakeholders should invest more in science education while curriculum planners and implementers should ensure that science in schools is taught in a way that helps to change the mindset and psyche of our people. This is the only way scientific knowledge can benefit society and bring about sustainable development.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past fifty years, the concept of scientific literacy was introduced to the science education community by (Hurd, 1958). There has been considerable debate over the various meanings entailed by science (Shamos, 1995; Laugksch, 2000; Fensham, 2002; Roberts, 2007). Scientific literacy and several closely related terms, like science literacy or public understanding of science are very much a part of the landscape of science education writing and research of the past half century. No ultimate consensus has been reached on the definition of the concept.

However, according to Hurd, (1998), scientific literacy is seen as a civic competency required for national thinking about science in relation to personal, social, political, economic problems and issues that one is likely to meet throughout life. In a much earlier analysis of this concept, Roberts (1983) suggested that scientific literacy has so many interpretations that it now means virtually everything to do with science education and it had come to be an umbrella concept to signify the purposes of teaching science in schools. During the early 1960s, scientific literacy was primarily a concept about curriculum goals. It suggests in very broad terms what the overall character of school science should be about and what it should emphasize. This means that scientific literacy as a concept may vary from day to day, but the fact remains that the concept still occupies a central position in aims and objectives for many contemporary curriculum reform projects (e.g. All American Advancement in Science, AAAS, 1989, 1993, 2001; Turkey Ministry of Education, TME, 2006). Since the 1960s educational reform, it has become a continuous worldwide movement in order to promote students literacy in different disciplines.

Universities, as other schools, are one of the places that prepare students for the real world and real life. In realizing this aim, universities must help their students gain scientific literacy abilities and grow scientifically literate citizens (Miller, 1998). This is necessary because of the challenge of living in a modern world. In addition, a scientifically literate individual has access to a wide range of employment

opportunities and is better prepared to respond to the introduction of new technologies. Moreover, he/she is better able to cope with the demands of everyday life in an increasingly technology-dominated society (Osborne, 1998).

Amplifying these views, Okoronka (2007) opined that in the new millennium, we have to teach science to our children who represent the future in order to equip them. He further stated that there is a new but fast growing trend of teaching science to make for a scientifically literate society in which every citizen will be made to imbibe and appreciate the science culture. He suggested that this would imply that the 21st century science teacher must brace up to the challenges of not only teaching the few would be future scientists but also teaching the larger number of non-scientists whom the demands of our age have imposed on him to expose to the rudiments of science. He concluded that this is the only way to make every member of society live meaningfully within our scientifically and technologically situated age.

Superstitious beliefs have been found in a diverse range of cultures for thousands of years (Jahoda, 1969) and polls show that these beliefs continue to thrive in modern times. The clearest demographic correlate of superstitious beliefs is gender. According to Vyse (1997) most superstitious beliefs are more often held by women than men. In some studies, a low educational level has been connected to superstitious beliefs (Otis & Alcock, 1982; Za'rour, 1972), but in general, the results have been inconsistent (The National Science Foundation, 2006; Vyse, 1997). Science education curriculum at the primary and secondary school level have a major goal of inculcating scientific literacy into learners.

The objective of this study therefore is to determine the superstitious beliefs of Adamawa state students in tertiary institutions as indicator of level of scientific literacy in Adamawa State. The study equally determined whether there were gender differences and stereotypes in the superstitious beliefs of respondents as well as the relationship between superstitious beliefs and level of education. To achieve these objectives a research question was raised and two null hypotheses stated to guide the study as follows:

Research Question

- (i) What are the superstitious beliefs of Adamawa state students in tertiary institutions on communication, sex, weather and environment?

Null hypotheses

Ho1 There is no significant difference between the superstitious beliefs of University students and College of Education students.

Ho2 There is no significant difference between male and female students inclination to superstitions

METHOD AND INSTRUMENTS

This study adopted survey research design to determine the superstitious beliefs of students of Adamawa State tertiary institutions. This is because survey research enables specific issues to be investigated through information gathering on people's opinion and belief over a large population. The population for this study comprised of all students in the tertiary institutions in Adamawa State who are indigenes. Two institutions were purposively selected as sample namely: Adamawa state University, Mubi (ADSU) and College of Education, Hong (COE). This is because the population of students in ADSU and COE is made up of more indigenes than other tertiary institutions in the state. Data were collected using questionnaire adapted from Uwalaka and Mutsuo (2002) which contained 25 items of a four point Likert scale format of Strongly agree, SA (4), Agree, A(3), Disagree, D(2) and Strongly Disagree, SD(1). The SA and A were collapsed together as A while the D and SD were collapsed into D.

RESULTS

Tables 1, 2, 3 and 4 show the percentage responses of the respondents on superstitious items on communication, sex, weather and environment respectively.

Table 1: Summary of Percentage Responses on Superstitious beliefs of Students in tertiary institution on communication

Items	Respondents		
	Agree (AG)%	disagree (DA)%	Total %
The white man is using “juju” in GSM network	62.8	37.2	100
The internet has some sort of rituals in the working process	59.6	40.3	100
It is believed that space satellites are using spirits and rituals in transmitting information	48.8	51.2	100
If a person bites his tongue while eating, it means somebody is calling him	53.7	46.3	100
If an owl cries it means an old person has died	47.0	53.0	100

Table 1 indicates that 62.8% of the respondents believe that the white man is using juju in GSM networks, followed by 59.6% which believe that the internet has some sort of rituals in the working process: The least belief from the above Table was if an owl cries it means an old person has died’ with 47.0% agree and 53% disagree. From the analysis, it is clear that the students are still inclined to superstitions beliefs on communication.

Table 2: Summary of Percentage Response on superstitious beliefs of students in tertiary institutions on Sex.

Items	RESPONDENTS’		
	Agree (AG)%	Disagree (DA)%	Total %
Bareness is as a result of evil spirit.	57.33	42.65	100
If a man eat food from a cooking pot, he will not bear a child	57.2	42.8	100
A woman who is not circumcised will be promiscuous	62.2	37.8	100
When a lizard cross over a woman legs, it means she will soon get pregnant	59.7	40.3	100
when a woman hates to get married, it means evil spirits have married her	40.8	59.2	100

Table 2 indicates that 62.2% of the respondents agree that a woman who is not circumcised will be promiscuous, followed by 59.7% which agree that when a lizard crosses over a woman legs, it means she will soon get pregnant: The least belief from the table was when a woman hates to get married, it means

evil spirits have married her, with 40.8% agree and 59.2% disagree. From the analysis, it is evident that the students are inclined to superstitious beliefs on sex.

Table 3: Summary of Percentage Response on superstitious belief of students in tertiary institutions on weather.

Items	RESPONDENTS'		
	Agree (AG)	Disagree (DA)	Total
It is bad to light torch and point it to the sky at night	56.4	43.6	100
When there is an eclipse of the moon, people should sacrifice a 'he goat' and beat drums to avert an impending danger	28.5	71.5	100
People should not count the stars at night	66.2	33.8	100
People should not sweep at night	82.6	17.4	100
When a thunder strikes a person dead, it indicates that the person's hands are not clean.	51.3	48.7	100

Table 3 indicates that 82.6% of the respondents believe that people should not sweep at night, followed by 66.2% which believe that people should not count the stars at night, followed by 56.4% who believe that it is bad to light torch and point it to the sky at night and 51.3% who believe that when thunder strikes a person dead, the persons hands are not clean. The least belief from the Table was when there is an eclipse of the moon people should sacrifice a He Goat and beat drums with 28.5% agree and 71.5% disagree From the analysis, it is evident that the students are still inclined to superstitions beliefs on weather .

Table 4: Summary of Percentage Response on superstitious belief of students in tertiary institutions on environment.

Items	Respondents		
	Agree (AG)%	Disagree (DA)%	Total %
When you push a firewood with your leg while cooking then the people to eat the food will fight	67.33	32.65	100
When a dead child is buried facing upward, it closes the mothers womb.	37.2	62.8	100
People should not talk or sing while taking bath	72.8	27.2	100
Evil spirits call people and they die if they answer	49.7	50.3	100
When a dog leaves the owners house to a neighboring house then the owner will die.	50.2	49.8	100S

Table 4 indicates that 72.2% of the respondents believe that people should not talk or sing while taking bath, followed by 67.33% which believe that when you push a firewood with your leg while cooking, then the people to eat the food will fight the least belief from the Table was that when a dead child is buried facing upward, it will closes the mother's womb with 37.2% agree and 62.8% disagree. From the analysis, it is clear that the students are inclined to superstitious beliefs on environment.

Table 5: Z–test for Comparison of Superstitions Inclination between University and College of education Students

Level of Education	Number (N)	Mean (\bar{X})	Standard deviation (SD)	Z-crit	Z-cal	Degree of freedom (DF)
University Students	374	43.80	7.245	0.121	1.96	766
College of Education students	394	43.96	7.835			

Table 5, shows that the superstitious inclination of college of education students and University students does not differ significantly. Calculated z-value from Table 6 is 1.96 which is greater than critical value of 0.121 considering 95% level of significance and 766 degree of freedom. Therefore, the hypotheses that states that there is no significant difference between the superstitious beliefs of University students and College of Education students, is not rejected.

Table 6: Z–test for Comparison of Superstition Inclination in Male and female respondents

Gender	Number (N)	Mean (\bar{X})	Standard deviation (SD)	Z-crit	Z-cal	Degree of freedom (DF)
Male	392	41.56	7.056	1.960	10.141	766
Female	376	46.06	7.151			

Table 6, showed that calculated z-value was 10.141 which is greater than the z-critical value 1.96, considering 5% error level. Therefore, it can be inferred (with at least 95%, confidence) that inclination to superstition in females is more than males. Therefore the second null hypothesis is not rejected which states that there is no significant difference between male and female Adamawa students superstitious beliefs.

DISCUSSION

Tables 1, 2, 3 and 4 indicate the percentage responses of the respondents on superstitious items on communication, sex, weather and environment respectively. From the analysis it is evident that Adamawa state students in tertiary institution believe most on superstitions on weather, followed by sex followed by environment and lastly communication. This finding is in agreement with research finding by Patel (1984) found that, majority of Indians had belief in superstition of their immediate environment

The mean inclination to superstitions in COE students is slightly more than that of University students. The z-test indicated that there is no significant difference between University students and College of education students' inclination to superstition. This finding is similar to that by Patel and Sanithi (1984) that superstitious beliefs are prevalent among people of all levels of formal education. Another finding of the study is that inclination to superstitious was more in female students than there male counterparts. This is in agreement with Shanooshii (2003); Zebb and Barbara (2001) and Peltzer (2002). Who found that

intentionally or unintentionally women incline to superstitions more than men because they rely on their feelings more than men and incline more to tradition.

Implication and conclusion

The findings of this study imply that the superstitious beliefs of students tend to persist even after they have finished secondary education and entered into tertiary institution. This further implies that the aims and objective of science education implemented through the teaching of physics, chemistry, mathematics and biology in secondary schools is not being attained. This calls for more concerted effort on the part of stakeholders in science education (government, science and mathematics teachers, science and mathematics textbooks authors) to adopt techniques and measures that will make science more authentic to the learner in confronting problems within his/her immediate environment. This will enable the average science student to be able to relate and use the scientific theories, principles and laws to explain events and phenomena in the immediate environment. After all, science education is supposed to help change the mindset and psyche of people. This is the only way scientific knowledge can benefit society and bring about sustainable development.

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